

Random number generation in digital ledger technology is an unsolved game theoretical problem. The issue has to do with trust: how can you know that an entity that claims to have generated a number by random, actually did so? The solution to this problem is analogous to the solution of validation in the Nakamoto consensus in general: distribute control and hope that the majority is honest.

The foundation of distributed majority agreement in both this solution, and in the Nakamoto consensus, is a mechanism to allocate control in a distributed way. This was historically done in a representative democracy with one-person-one-vote, then in digital form originally done in Bitcoin with one-cpu-one-vote, followed by one-coin-one-vote, and more recently work is being done to finally adapt Nakamoto consensus for one-person-one-vote.

As an example of how to organize a random number Oracle by majority vote, here is an implementation in a Solidity smart contract, using one-cpu-one-vote to allocate votes.

```

contract RandomNumberOracle {
    uint constant period;

    function t() public view returns (uint) { return (block.number / period) * period; }

    uint nonce;

    mapping (uint => bytes32[]) blockhashes;
    mapping (uint => mapping (uint => uint)) points;

    mapping (uint => uint[]) leaderboard;
    mapping (uint => mapping (uint => uint)) leaderboardIndex;
    mapping (uint => mapping (uint => uint)) upperBound;
    mapping (uint => mapping (uint => uint)) lowerBound;

    function getRandomNumber() public view returns (uint) {
        return uint(blockhashes[t()-period*2][leaderboard[t()-period][0]]);
    }

    function vote(uint _id) public {
        require(msg.sender == block.coinbase && nonce != block.number);
        nonce = block.number;
        blockhashes[t()].push(blockhash(block.number - 1));

        if(blockhashes[t()-period].length == 0) return;

        require(_id < blockhashes[t()-period].length);

        if(points[t()][_id] == 0) {
            leaderboardIndex[t()][_id] = leaderboard[t()].length;
            if(upperBound[t()][1] == 0) upperBound[t()][1] = leaderboard[t()].length;
            leaderboard[t()].push(_id);
        }
        else {
            uint index = leaderboardIndex[t()][_id];
            uint nextBucket = upperBound[t()][points[t()][_id]];
            if(nextBucket != index) {
                (leaderboard[t()][nextBucket], leaderboard[t()][index]) = (leaderboard[t()][index], leaderboard[t()][nextBucket]);
            }
            if(lowerBound[t()][points[t()][_id]] == nextBucket) {
                lowerBound[t()][points[t()][_id]] = 0;
                upperBound[t()][points[t()][_id]] = 0;
            }
            else upperBound[t()][points[t()][_id]]--;

            if(upperBound[t()][points[t()][_id]+1] == 0) upperBound[t()][points[t()][_id]+1] = nextBucket;
            lowerBound[t()][points[t()][_id]+1] = nextBucket;
        }
        points[t()][_id]++;
    }
}

```